

Stabilities and Thermodynamics of La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III), Sm(III) Complexes of *n*-Butyl Thio Glycolate

R. S. SAXENA and M. C. SAXENA

Department of Chemistry, Malaviya Regional Engineering College, Jaipur-302 004

Manuscript received 17 January 1978, revised 19 September 1978, accepted 6 October 1978.

Complexation of trivalent La, Ce, Pr and Sm with *n*-butyl thio glycolate in 40% ethanol water mixture (V/V) have been investigated by potentiometric titration techniques at a constant ionic strength ($\mu=0.1M$ NaClO₄) at temperature of 20°, 30° and 40°. Formation curves reveal the formation of 1:1 and 1:3 complexes in each case and their stabilities determined by Calvin and Melchior's extension of Bjerrum method, follow the order $La^{3+} < Ce^{3+} < Pr^{3+} < Sm^{3+}$, which has been explained on the basis of born relation.

The over all changes in thermodynamic functions ΔG , ΔH , ΔS for the complexation reactions are also reported at 30°.

IN view of the wide recognition of organo-sulphur compounds in medicinal, industrial and agricultural fields, a large number of such compounds have been studied by Saxena *et al*¹⁻⁴. In sequence to our earlier work, this paper reports the complexing tendencies of some rare earth metals *viz.*, La³⁺, Ce³⁺, Pr³⁺, Sm³⁺ with *n*-butyl thio glycolate, determination of their stability constants and various thermodynamic parameters.

Experimental

n-Butyl thio glycolate (referred herein as RSH) was obtained from Evan's Chemetics, New York and other Chemicals were of Anal-R-grade. Freshly prepared solutions were used to avoid the effects of ageing and air-oxidation. pH was measured on Cambridge pH meter with glass-calomel electrode assembly. Titrations were carried out in absence and presence of metal ion against standard alkali in oxygen-free nitrogen atmosphere.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometry: The magnitude of proton displacement was determined by titrating the solution containing RSH and the metal ion in different molar ratios against standard NaOH in order to establish the stoichiometry of the complex species formed during the interaction of metal ion and RSH.

A slight addition of NaOH to the ligand results in raising the pH abruptly (Fig. 1, Curve 1) signifying the non-titrability of the proton of -SH group under the experimental conditions. The addition of an equimolar concentration of metal ion greatly alters the shape of free ligand titration curve (Fig. 1, Curve 4) indicating the complex formation which

Fig. 1. pH titrations of the solutions
(1) 4.0 mM RSH ;
(2) 4.0 mM RSH + 1.0 mM Sm(III)
(3) 4.0 mM RSH + 2.0 mM Sm(III)
(4) 4.0 mM RSH + 4.0 mM Sm(III)

results in the lowering of buffer region due to the displacement of proton.

where, M stands for La³⁺,
Ce³⁺, Pr³⁺ and Sm³⁺.

Since the extent of proton displacement depends on the relative affinity of ligand for H⁺ and the metal ion, it is clear from the curve that the interaction of M³⁺ ion with RSH is sufficient to compete with a relatively high (H⁺). The inflection at m=3 (m being the moles of NaOH per mole of RSH) may suggest the formation of either M(RS)(OH)₂ or M(RS)₂ and M(OH)₂ in accordance with the following equations :

The appearance of precipitate during the titration rules out the possibility of formation of hydroxo-metal complex⁵ (eqn. 2) and supports the formation of $M(RS)_3$ and $M(OH)_3$ eqn. (3) i.e. 1 : 3 as highest complex.

With the metal and the ligand in the ratio 1 : 2 and 1 : 4, the inflection is obtained at $M=1.5$ and 0.75 (Fig. 1. Curve 3, 2) which confirms the formation of 1 : 3 as highest complex.

Stability constants :

Calvin and Melchior's⁶ extension of Bjerrum's⁷ method has been employed for the determination of stability constants of the complex. The pH titrations of RSH solution with ionic strength $\mu=0.1 M$ ($NaClO_4$) in absence and presence of metal ion were carried out at 20°, 30° and 40° against 0.1 M NaOH and concentration of ligand bound, calculated from the horizontal distance between the corresponding curves, was divided by the total metal ion concentration to obtain formation function (\bar{n}). At any pH, the value of the free ligand concentration, [A], was calculated from the relation

$$[A] = \frac{[RSH]_{Total} - [RSH]_{bound}}{[H^+]/K_a + 1}$$

where K_a , the dissociation constant of RSH determined polarographically⁸, is 3.98×10^{-10} . The formation curves obtained at different temperatures by plotting \bar{n} vs. $-\log(A)$ reveal the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 3 complexes for all the four metals La^{3+} , Ce^{3+} , Pr^{3+} and Sm^{3+} . The trend of their stabilities follow the order (Table 1). $La < Ce < Pr < Sm$

orbitals by electrons in the 5s and 5p orbitals. Hybridization would involve normally unoccupied higher energy orbitals (e.g. 5d, 6s, 6p) and this may be expected to occur with the most strongly coordinated ligands. Lanthanides, therefore, normally form ionic compounds. The possibility of covalent interaction, however, cannot be completely ruled out as reported in the case of acetyl-acetone chelates of lanthanides⁹.

If the bonds are ionic, the Born relation $E=e^2(1-1/D)/2r$ should hold for the energy change on complexation of a gaseous ion of charge e and radius r in a medium of dielectric constant D . Since the stability constant is related directly to this energy, the $\log K$ values should increase linearly with e^2/r . The plots of e^2/r vs. $\log K_1$ and $\log K_3$ values of the metal complex studied (Fig. 2, curve 1, 2) do not however, exhibit any linear increase of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_3$ with increase in e^2/r .

Fig. 2. pH titration of the solution
(1) Plot of $\log K_1$ vs. e^2/r .
(2) Plot of $\log K_3$ vs. e^2/r .

TABLE - 1. STABILITIES OF LA(III), CE(III), PR(III), SM(III) COMPLEX OF *n*-BUTYL THIOGLYCOLATE

Metal complexes	20°C			30°C			40°C		
	Log K_1	Log K_3	Log B	Log K_1	Log K_3	Log B	Log K_1	Log K_3	Log B
La(III)	4.30	3.70	8.00	4.22	3.70	7.92	4.15	3.70	7.85
Ce(III)	4.57	4.07	8.65	4.55	4.02	8.57	4.40	3.98	8.38
Pr(III)	4.70	4.20	8.90	4.65	4.17	8.82	4.60	4.11	8.71
Sm(III)	5.00	4.50	9.50	4.95	4.45	9.40	4.90	4.37	9.27

A plausible explanation for this trend is that the lanthanide metal ions differ from each other in number of electrons in the 4f orbitals which are effectively shielded from interaction with ligand

Thermodynamic functions :

The values of overall changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) accompanying complexation reactions have been determined at

TABLE - 2. THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS FOR LA(III), CE(III), PR(III), SM(III) COMPLEXES OF *n*-BUTYL THIOGLYCOLATE

Metal complexes	ΔG (K. cal/mole)	ΔS (K. cal/mole)	ΔH (cal/deg./mole)
Lanthanum	-10.98	-3.19	25.68
Cerium	-11.89	-3.97	26.13
Praseodymium	-12.23	-3.36	29.25
Sammarium	-13.03	-3.20	25.92

30° with the help of standard equations¹⁰ and are summarized in Table 2.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to U. G. C. New Delhi for grant of fellowship to one of them (M. C. S)

References

1. R. S. SAXENA, K. C. GUPTA and M. L. MITTAL, *Cand. J. Chem.* 1968, 46, 311.
2. R. S. SAXENA and S. S. SHEELWANT, *J. inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1973, 35, 1383.
3. R. S. SAXENA and M. C. SAXENA, *Indian J. Chem.* 1976, 14A, 628.
4. R. S. SAXENA and M. C. SAXENA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 52, 633.
5. S. CHAMBEREK and A. E. MARTELL, *Organic Sequestering Agents*, Wiley, New York, 1959, p, 72.
6. M. CALVIN and N. C. MELCHIOR, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 3270.
7. J. BJERRUM, 'Metal Amine Formation in Aqueous Solutions', Hasse, Copenhagen (1941).
8. R. S. SAXENA and M. C. SAXENA, *Montaschefte fur Chime.* 1976, 107, 1423.
9. T. D. MOELLER, *Chem. Rev.*, 1965, 65, 1.
10. K. B. YATSIMIRSKII and V. P. VASILEV, *Instability Constants of Complex Compounds*, Pergamon Press, Oxford (1960).